

Stakeholder-driven circular economy on marginal lands: Governance and sustainability trade-offs in biomass value chains[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Circular economy (CE) models have potential to advance sustainability in biomass-based value chains, but implementation on marginal lands is constrained by governance fragmentation, limited financing, and diverging stakeholder priorities. Using a mixed-methods approach—including stakeholder surveys, thematic coding, and concept mapping—this study examines governance expectations across seven international case contexts in Europe, South Africa, and Argentina. The results reveal pronounced differences across groups: businesses and investors prioritize infrastructure, financing mechanisms, and market stability; farmers emphasize land-use flexibility, compensation schemes, and long-term support; policymakers and environmental and conservation organizations focus on regulatory coherence, biodiversity protection, and inclusive governance; while research and innovation actors call for strengthened coordination, knowledge exchange, and locally adapted monitoring systems. In Global South cases, social equity issues—especially related to land access, participation, and benefit sharing—emerged as critical concerns. Across groups and countries, shared expectations for biobased products centered on climate and biodiversity benefits, affordability, traceability, and alignment with local needs and CE principles. Concept mapping illustrates interlinkages between stakeholder-defined priorities, governance gaps, and technical constraints, offering insight into underlying sustainability trade-offs. The findings highlight stakeholder governance as a central enabler of CE transitions, emphasizing the need for multi-level, participatory coordination, stable financial support, and cross-sectoral alignment. These insights contribute to context-sensitive strategies for circular bioeconomy development on marginal lands and support progress toward SDG 12.5, while reinforcing synergies with SDGs 13 and 15 on climate and biodiversity goals.

1. Introduction

The circular economy (CE) is increasingly recognized as a transformative framework for decoupling economic growth from environmental degradation in response to global sustainability challenges. CE principles contribute directly to SDG 12 on responsible consumption and production by promoting resource efficiency, waste prevention, and systemic innovation (Roy et al., 2022; Kirchherr and van Santen, 2019). Circular business models, grounded in closed-loop supply chains and life cycle thinking, aim to minimize environmental impacts while generating new economic opportunities (Ghisellini et al., 2018; Geissdoerfer et al., 2020), thus supporting the objectives of SDG 12.5 to substantially reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling, and reuse.

Biomass value chains represent a particularly promising domain for

applying CE strategies, especially in underutilized landscapes such as marginal lands, areas characterized by poor soil quality, limited infrastructure, and restricted agricultural productivity. These landscapes, while traditionally overlooked, offer potential for producing bio-based resources without competing with food systems (Burland and von Cosset, 2023; Panoutsou et al., 2022). Within this context, CE practices such as industrial symbiosis and cascading biomass use may contribute to carbon sequestration, biodiversity restoration, and rural development (Hsiao and Hu, 2024; Toplicean and Datcu, 2024).

However, realizing circularity in biomass systems on marginal lands requires more than technological innovation or environmental benefits, it hinges on the alignment of diverse stakeholder interests and effective governance frameworks. Biomass value chains are embedded in complex socio-ecological systems, where the perspectives of farmers, industry actors, public authorities, investors, and civil society play a

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critical role in shaping CE adoption. Governance mechanisms that coordinate these interests and mediate trade-offs are essential for transitioning from theory to practice.

While the CE concept offers a valuable lens for evaluating sustainability trade-offs across biomass value chains on marginal lands, its practical implementation remains constrained by systemic challenges. These include market volatility, fragmented governance structures, and limited investment incentives (Iacovidou et al., 2017; D'amato and Korhonen, 2021). Regulatory misalignments and weak coordination among stakeholders further impede the scalability and effectiveness of CE initiatives (Mendoza et al., 2022; Kandpal et al., 2024). Overcoming these challenges requires integrated and adaptive governance models that reflect local socio-environmental contexts and actively involve stakeholders.

Although research on CE transitions is growing, it has largely focused on technological innovation and environmental performance, often overlooking the stakeholder governance dimensions that shape CE feasibility, particularly in land-based bioeconomy systems. Despite extensive CE applications in manufacturing and industrial waste management, their translation to biomass systems on marginal lands remains limited and fragmented (Faulkner et al., 2024; Korhonen et al., 2018; Dahiya et al., 2020).

This study fills this gap by providing one of the first multi-country, stakeholder-driven investigations of governance expectations, sustainability trade-offs, and biobased value chain design in marginal land settings. Drawing on empirical data from the EU-funded MarginUp! project and using a mixed-methods approach, including stakeholder surveys, qualitative thematic analysis, and concept mapping, it explores how stakeholder-defined concerns, governance barriers, and sustainability priorities shape the feasibility and scalability of CE solutions in these complex landscapes.

The study contributes to the literature on CE and sustainable production by offering an integrated analytical framework that links stakeholder perspectives with governance dynamics and sustainability objectives. It provides actionable insights into how circular biomass systems can be designed and governed to meet local needs while addressing broader ecological and policy challenges.

Accordingly, the study is guided by the following research questions:

- (i) What primary barriers and concerns do stakeholders identify for adopting CE practices within biomass value chains?
- (ii) How do stakeholders prioritize CE strategies, including market viability, resource efficiency, regulatory coherence, and ecosystem restoration in biomass production?
- (iii) Which governance and policy mechanisms can effectively support and scale circular biomass models in marginal land contexts?

2. Literature review

This section provides the conceptual foundations for analyzing CE transitions in biomass value chains on marginal lands. It first discusses sustainability trade-offs and governance tensions in CE implementation, and then introduces a stakeholder-centered framing aligned with circularity goals.

2.1. Circular economy models in biomass value chains

CE models represent a fundamental shift in the design and governance of biomass value chains, aiming to decouple economic growth from resource depletion and environmental degradation. Within the broader bioeconomy, CE principles emphasize material circularity, cascading biomass use, and the systemic redesign of production systems to minimize waste and close resource loops (Toplicean and Datcu, 2024; Blair et al., 2021). These approaches are essential not only for enhancing resource efficiency but also for stimulating innovation in bio-based products, supporting resilient local economies, and contributing to

sustainability goals such as climate neutrality and biodiversity conservation (Simioni et al., 2024; Shah et al., 2023; Hinderer et al., 2021).

Recent literature identifies several CE strategies particularly relevant to biomass systems, including regenerative agriculture, agro-industrial symbiosis, cascading biomass applications, and circular supply chains. These strategies prioritize ecological regeneration alongside economic circularity and are increasingly viewed as instrumental in enabling a just transition in rural and industrial regions (Hsiao and Hu, 2024; Geissdoerfer et al., 2020). However, their implementation remains challenging, especially in geographically and economically constrained settings such as marginal lands.

Although technical innovations in biomass valorization—such as precision agriculture, pyrolysis, anaerobic digestion, and advanced biorefinery platforms—have progressed substantially (Kardung et al., 2021), the translation of these solutions into practice is hindered by systemic barriers. These include fragmented policy environments, infrastructural limitations, market uncertainties surrounding emerging bio-based products, and inadequate institutional support (Ding, 2025; Schipfer et al., 2024). Crucially, the success of CE models depends not only on technological maturity but also on enabling governance conditions—namely, cross-sectoral coordination, policy coherence, and innovation systems that are responsive to local socio-ecological contexts (Mendoza et al., 2022).

2.2. Marginal lands in circular biomass production

Marginal lands are increasingly recognized as strategic assets for expanding biomass production without displacing food crops or degrading high-value ecosystems. Characterized by biophysical constraints such as poor soil fertility, water scarcity, salinity, or historical degradation, these lands have traditionally been excluded from mainstream agricultural and industrial use (Burland and von Cossel, 2023; Von Cossel et al., 2019). However, recent longitudinal studies show that the functionality and classification of such lands are not static, but shaped by dynamic land system transitions and shifting socio-ecological pressures over time (Orozco et al., 2024). Yet, with appropriate management, they can support multifunctional land use, including biomass cultivation, ecological restoration, and carbon sequestration (Edrisi et al., 2022; Schröder et al., 2018).

Implementing circular bioeconomy models on marginal lands presents both sustainability opportunities and trade-offs. Environmental risks include soil erosion, habitat disturbance, and unintended land-use intensification (Sun et al., 2024; Aszalós et al., 2017). Economically, marginal land development often requires substantial initial investment and faces uncertain returns. Social and institutional barriers—such as land tenure insecurity and fragmented governance—further constrain scale-up potential (Ogwu et al., 2025; Jha et al., 2024).

The MarginUp! project explores how these challenges and opportunities manifest in seven case studies across diverse marginal contexts. For example, turnip rape is cultivated for biofuel and feed on boreal soils in Sweden; black locust and lavender are grown on former lignite mines in Greece; and hemp and kenaf support green building material production on degraded lands in Spain. Other cases include wetland biomass use in Germany, short-rotation coppice on sandy soils in Hungary, saline soil remediation in Argentina, and bioenergy production from invasive species in South Africa.

These illustrative cases demonstrate that the effective deployment of circular biomass systems on marginal lands requires context-sensitive, integrated strategies—combining ecological restoration, inclusive governance, innovation ecosystems, and risk-mitigation mechanisms tailored to local conditions.

2.3. Stakeholder perspectives and governance in circular economy

Effective stakeholder engagement is widely recognized as a key enabler in the implementation of CE strategies, particularly in biomass

value chains operating on marginal lands. These systems are embedded in complex socio-ecological contexts shaped by multiple, and often competing, stakeholder interests. Policymakers, farmers, industry actors, investors, researchers, and civil society representatives hold divergent priorities related to land use, environmental protection, innovation, and economic viability (Sukprasert and Phadungkit, 2024; Diaz et al., 2022; Skene, 2022). Their perspectives influence not only the design of CE models but also the pace and direction of their adoption, often revealing tensions between sustainability goals and financial constraints (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020; Aljamal et al., 2024).

Governance mechanisms are central to managing these tensions and aligning diverse stakeholder objectives. Yet, governance in CE transitions, particularly on marginal lands, is frequently challenged by fragmented regulations, institutional overlaps, weak economic incentives, and limited integration of local actors in decision-making (Schipfer et al., 2024; Kandpal et al., 2024). Inclusivity remains underdeveloped in many CE policies, particularly regarding primary producers, who often lack the institutional support needed for full participation (Park and Grundmann, 2023). Even well-conceived CE models risk failure if the institutional environment lacks coherence, inclusivity, or adaptive capacity. Recent literature increasingly calls for multi-level governance frameworks that link national-level policy ambitions with localized innovation systems, while fostering participation, transparency, and system learning (Sharma et al., 2024; Schipfer et al., 2022; Achillas and Bochtis, 2020).

To structure this interdisciplinary discourse, Table 1 provides a synthesis of key literature contributions across three interrelated dimensions: CE Models, Stakeholder Perspectives, and Governance and Policy Frameworks. This conceptual scaffold informs the empirical analysis presented in this study, which draws on stakeholder survey data, thematic coding, and concept mapping to explore how governance challenges and stakeholder priorities intersect within circular biomass value chains on marginal lands.

2.4. Research gap and contribution of this study

Although the circular bioeconomy has received increasing policy attention and academic scrutiny, much of the existing literature remains focused on technological innovation and environmental performance, with comparatively limited attention to social, governance, and place-based implementation dynamics—particularly in underutilized or resource-constrained territories such as marginal lands (Nifatova et al., 2024; Schipfer et al., 2024; Sherwood, 2020). Existing analytical frameworks often fall short in addressing the complex interplay between stakeholder interests, land-use conditions, institutional capacity, and policy coherence (Leipold et al., 2023; Mendoza et al., 2022; Watson et al., 2018).

Table 1
Synthesis of literature on circular economy in biomass value chains.

Aspect	Author(s)	Year	Primary focus	Key insights
CE models	Geissdoerfer et al.	2020	Circular business models	Cross-sector strategies enhance resource efficiency and support CE transitions.
	Toplicean & Datcu	2024	Regenerative agricultural practices	Regional adaptive agriculture enables sustainable biomass production.
	Stegmann et al.	2020	Bio-based product innovation	CE innovations reduce environmental impacts across sectors.
Governance & policy	Panoutsou et al.	2021	Resource cycle integration	Holistic CE frameworks improve biomass supply chain coordination.
	Schipfer et al.	2024	System integration in governance	Integrated governance is essential for CE and bioeconomy transitions.
	Kandpal et al.	2024	Governance barriers	Governance gaps hinder CE implementation on marginal lands.
	Sharma et al.	2024	Multi-level policy frameworks	Aligning national and local policies supports CE governance.
	Achillas & Bochtis	2020	Participatory governance	Stakeholder-inclusive approaches improve transition management.
Stakeholder perspectives	Korhonen et al.	2018	Governance complexity	Early attention to institutional barriers improves CE policy alignment.
	Sukprasert & Phadungkit	2024	Agricultural stakeholder roles	Farmers' inclusion in CE models improves relevance and impact.
	Diaz et al.	2022	Public engagement in CE	Local involvement is essential for equitable CE transitions.
	Skene	2022	Societal transition dynamics	CE adoption requires social acceptance and systemic thinking.
	Kirchherr & van Santen	2019	Stakeholder diversity in CE	Varied stakeholder motives shape CE success and tensions.

This study addresses these critical gaps by investigating how stakeholder priorities, governance challenges, and regulatory frameworks interact to shape the feasibility and sustainability of circular biomass value chains in marginal contexts. Drawing on empirical data from the EU-funded *MarginUp!* project, the research examines seven diverse cases across Europe, Argentina, and South Africa—each representing distinct ecological, technological, and institutional configurations. These cases provide a robust basis for identifying common patterns and context-specific trade-offs in CE implementation.

Methodologically, the study makes an important contribution by integrating stakeholder survey data, qualitative thematic coding, and concept mapping into a unified analytical framework. This mixed-method design enables both depth and breadth—capturing detailed stakeholder perspectives while also visualizing the interdependencies between governance barriers, sustainability objectives, and CE strategies. The use of concept mapping, in particular, offers a novel approach that extends existing stakeholder and governance frameworks by visually synthesizing the interconnections between sustainability priorities, perceived barriers, and governance needs. While prior research has focused on listing stakeholder views or analyzing themes separately, this study's approach enables a systems-level understanding of how these elements interact within the context of CE transitions on marginal lands.

By aligning empirical findings with multi-level governance theory and circular bioeconomy frameworks, this study advances both theoretical understanding and policy relevance. It contributes to the development of inclusive, context-sensitive governance approaches for circular transitions in biomass value chains on marginal lands, where ecological fragility and institutional fragmentation often coexist.

3. Methodology

This section explains the research design and methods used in the study. It describes the mixed-methods approach, including survey structure, qualitative coding, and concept mapping, and introduces the seven international case contexts across Europe, South Africa, and Argentina.

3.1. Research design

This study applies a comprehensive mixed-methods design to investigate stakeholder perspectives, governance challenges, and sustainability priorities within CE strategies for biomass value chains on marginal lands. The approach integrates quantitative, qualitative, and concept mapping techniques to ensure methodological triangulation and a robust interpretation of findings.

First, quantitative analysis was conducted to assess stakeholder perceptions of potential risks associated with biomass value chain

market actors, governance enablers, and knowledge institutions, and served as a structured basis for comparative analysis across countries and use cases. To address potential bias from underrepresented groups (notably public authorities, environmental NGOs, and investors), we applied methodological triangulation, cross-validating quantitative results with qualitative insights from open-ended responses, ensuring that even single-response views were thematically coded and incorporated into the analysis.

Respondents were recruited through a mixed outreach strategy. The survey was initially launched via project partners and targeted toward stakeholders directly involved in the project's pilot cases or associated with the biomass value chains under study. These included organizations participating in the project or closely collaborating with it. In parallel, the survey link was disseminated more broadly through professional platforms (e.g., LinkedIn), mailing lists, and partner networks, which also attracted responses from stakeholders external to the project. As a result, the final sample includes both project-involved actors and a smaller share of independent or affiliated experts, ensuring diverse perspectives across different levels of engagement.

A total of 130 valid responses were collected and analyzed. As illustrated in Fig. 2a, Research, Education & Innovation Organizations made up the largest share of participants (43 %, 56 respondents), followed by Farmers & Agricultural Sector and Industry & Bio-based Product Companies (each 15 %, 20 respondents). Investors & Market Actors accounted for 12 % (15 respondents), while Environmental & Conservation Organizations (5 %, 6 respondents) and Public Authorities & Policymakers (4 %, 5 respondents) were least represented. This distribution reflects a strong research and practitioner presence, while also identifying underrepresented stakeholder groups important for inclusive

governance.

3.3. Case selection and description

Building upon the illustrative examples introduced in Section 2.2, this section provides an in-depth overview of the seven biomass value chains analyzed in this study, developed under the EU-funded *MarginUp!* project. These cases were strategically selected to capture diverse bio-physical, socio-economic, and governance contexts across marginal lands in Europe, Latin America, and southern Africa. The diversity of ecological zones, land-use histories, biomass types, and institutional configurations offers a robust foundation for a comparative analysis of CE implementation in land-constrained environments (Fig. 2b).

The case studies span five European countries including Sweden, Spain, Greece, Germany, and Hungary, as well as two international contexts, Argentina and South Africa. Each case reflects a unique intersection of marginal land typologies (e.g., saline soils, degraded peatlands, post-mining areas), biomass feedstocks, value chain applications, and enabling or constraining governance conditions. Collectively, they demonstrate how CE models can be adapted to site-specific realities, ranging from highly industrialized to semi-natural and socially complex landscapes.

Sweden: In boreal agricultural zones, turnip rape (*Brassica rapa*) is cultivated in rotation with cereals and ley for biodiesel and animal feed. Pressed cake and glycerol are valorized locally via biogas production and digestate reuse, forming a closed-loop system.

Spain: On Mediterranean low-yielding soils, hemp and kenaf are introduced into crop rotations to produce bio-based construction materials, biogas, and organic fertilizer, supporting circularity through

Fig. 2a. Stakeholder representation across countries in the survey (stacked bar chart showing survey respondent distribution by stakeholder group and country, highlighting group-level diversity).

Fig. 2b. Geographic distribution of survey respondents by country (this choropleth world map visualizes the total number of respondents from each country, highlighting differences in national participation in the survey).

nutrient cycling and diversified land use.

Greece: Former lignite mine lands are repurposed through the intercropping of black locust (*Robinia pseudoacacia*) and lavender, yielding biomass for wood panel production and cosmetic industries. The system provides additional ecological services such as phytoremediation and erosion control.

Germany: In rewetted peatlands of Brandenburg, reed canary grass and cattail are harvested and processed into erosion-protection panels and pellets. This approach supports low-input biomass use while contributing to wetland biodiversity and restoration goals.

Hungary: On semi-arid sandy soils, short-rotation woody crops such as sida and willow are used in cascading systems for oyster mushroom cultivation, biogas production, and animal feed—illustrating multi-output biomass valorization on marginal soils.

Argentina: In the saline and flood-prone landscapes of the Flooding Pampa, *Lotus tenuis*, rapeseed, and hemp are cultivated for forage, fertilizer, biofuel, and high-value applications (e.g., nanotech-enhanced products). This system addresses both land remediation and bioeconomy diversification.

South Africa: Although not part of pilot implementation, this case investigates the use of invasive alien tree species (e.g., *Acacia*) for decentralized bioenergy production, aligning environmental management objectives with local energy access solutions.

These case studies exemplify how CE strategies—such as cascading biomass use, nutrient recovery, renewable energy generation, and circular inputs—can be tailored to the ecological constraints and governance realities of marginal land settings. They also reveal a range of systemic barriers, including fragmented regulatory frameworks, infrastructural limitations, and market volatility, which must be addressed for effective scaling. A synthesis of key case attributes is presented in Table 2.

3.4. Data analysis

A structured mixed-methods approach was employed to generate comprehensive insights into stakeholder perceptions, sustainability priorities, and governance challenges associated with circular biomass value chains on marginal lands. The analysis integrated quantitative and qualitative data streams, enabling triangulation and reinforcing the validity of findings across methodological boundaries.

Quantitative analysis was conducted using Python specifically employing the Pandas, NumPy, Matplotlib, and Seaborn libraries. Stakeholder ratings from Q5 (perceived risks) and Q7 (sustainability priorities) were analyzed across countries and stakeholder groups. Comparative visualizations, including heatmaps and ranking charts, were used to identify cross-cutting patterns, highlight country-specific

Table 2
Overview of MarginUp! biomass value chains on marginal lands.

Country	Biomass type(s)	Marginal land type	Primary end use (s)	Main challenges
Sweden	Turnip rape (<i>Brassica rapa</i>)	Boreal underutilized cropland	Biodiesel, animal feed, biogas from by-products	Short growing season, crop rotation limits
Spain	Hemp, kenaf	Mediterranean low-yield soils	Building materials, biogas, organic fertilizer	Arid climate, market volatility
Greece	Black locust, lavender	Degraded lignite mine lands	Wood panels, cosmetics, phytoremediation	Soil degradation, climatic stress
Germany	Reed canary grass, cattail	Rewetted peatlands	Erosion-protection panels, pellets	Wetland management, biodiversity trade-offs
Hungary	Sida, willow	Semi-arid sandy soils	Mushroom substrate, biogas, animal feed	Water scarcity, limited infrastructure
Argentina	<i>Lotus tenuis</i> , rapeseed, hemp	Saline and flood-prone soils	Forage, fertilizers, biofuels, nanotech-enhanced bioproducts	Soil salinity, seasonal access, low productivity
South Africa	Invasive alien species (e.g., <i>Acacia</i>)	Bush-encroached rangelands	Bioenergy, land restoration, decentralized energy solutions	Invasive species control, institutional coordination

divergences, and surface critical sustainability concerns. These visual outputs supported the interpretation of systemic trends in stakeholder perspectives, enhancing the clarity and communicability of results.

Qualitative data, primarily from Q4, Q6, Q8, Q9, and Q12, were analyzed through reflexive thematic coding. Responses were processed in ATLAS.ti, where stakeholder inputs were inductively coded and subsequently grouped into higher-order thematic categories. These categories reflected recurring concerns, expectations, proposed measures, and governance conflicts. The process allowed for the development of narrative depth and contextual richness, uncovering dimensions that are not readily captured through closed-ended analysis.

To further examine how stakeholder concerns relate to broader CE domains, qualitative insights were translated into a concept map based on responses to Q4, Q6, Q8, Q9, and Q12. Co-occurrence analysis was applied to identify interlinkages between codes, which were grouped into seven strategic themes: governance and policy, economic and

market dimensions, technical and environmental factors, social and community considerations, CE framing, stakeholder conflicts, and sustainability needs. Code co-occurrence counts were generated using ATLAS.ti's analytical tools, and the resulting relationships were visualized using Python's NetworkX and Matplotlib libraries. In the concept map, green circular nodes represented stakeholder-derived themes, while blue square nodes signified overarching strategic categories. The strength of connections—expressed through edge thickness and weighted labels—indicated the frequency of co-mention across stakeholder responses.

Although this study does not conduct a formal Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA), the analysis incorporates stakeholder concerns across multiple stages of the biomass value chain. These include land cultivation, processing, market deployment, and downstream circular strategies such as cascading use, biofertilizer production, and material reuse. As such, the data-driven insights conceptually align with LCSA thinking by embedding life cycle perspectives within a governance-oriented and stakeholder-centered framework.

This integrated analytical design enabled cross-validation between methods, supported robust interpretation of stakeholder input, and increased the policy relevance and transferability of the findings. It provided both systemic clarity and practical depth, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of how CE models can be effectively operationalized in marginal land contexts.

4. Results

This section presents the empirical findings from the stakeholder survey and concept mapping. It is organized by sustainability dimensions, environmental, economic, institutional, and social, and highlights differences across stakeholder groups and regional contexts, followed by an integrative conceptual map.

4.1. Stakeholder perceptions of risks and barriers in biomass value chains on marginal lands

4.1.1. Quantitative risk perceptions by stakeholder group and country (Q5)

Stakeholders identified a range of concerns regarding the implementation of biomass value chains on marginal lands, grouped into environmental, economic, and governance-related risks. However, the overall likelihood of negative impacts was rated as low to moderate across most categories, indicating that while risks exist; they are not perceived as prohibitive. This suggests conditional stakeholder openness toward circular biomass models, assuming appropriate safeguards and governance mechanisms are in place.

Analysis across stakeholder groups revealed distinct patterns (Fig. 3). Environmental & Conservation Organizations and Technology & Service Providers reported the highest concern for environmental risks, such as soil degradation, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem capacity limits, with multiple ratings exceeding 1.4. Farmers & Agricultural Sector stakeholders expressed moderate concern for environmental risks but placed greater emphasis on issues tied to land access, livelihood security, and social equality. Industry & Bio-Based Product Companies and Investors & Market Actors focused primarily on economic risks, including production costs and market instability. Investor groups in particular rated most risks very low, with scores frequently below 1.0. Public Authorities & Policymakers did not show strong concern in any one domain, but their responses leaned toward regulatory themes such as knowledge transfer and institutional coordination. Research, Education & Innovation Organizations showed a balanced distribution of concern across all categories, consistent with their broader systems perspective.

National-level results further underscore the diversity of perspectives (Fig. 4). Stakeholders in Greece, Hungary, and Spain consistently assigned higher likelihood to environmental risks, particularly those associated with soil degradation and water quality. In contrast, German

Fig. 3. Stakeholder-specific perceptions of potential negative impacts in circular biomass value chains on marginal lands. Heatmap based on survey responses to Q5, showing the likelihood ratings of negative impacts across sustainability areas. Darker shades reflect higher perceived risk.

Fig. 4. Perceived negative impacts in circular biomass value chains on marginal lands, by country. Country-level comparison of stakeholder perceptions regarding potential negative impacts (Q5). Vertical axis shows sustainability areas; horizontal axis lists countries.

and Swedish responses focused more on production-related issues, such as input costs and production intensity. Argentina displayed moderate concern for economic viability and governance clarity. In South Africa, environmental and economic risks were rated lower, while concerns related to land tenure, social equity, and access to land stood out as the highest-rated issues—reflecting the country's socio-political context.

These findings demonstrate that stakeholder perceptions of risk in circular biomass systems are highly context-specific and shaped by institutional roles, geographic realities, and value chain experience. Importantly, the absence of uniformly high-risk assessments across the dataset reinforces the view that circular biomass development on marginal lands is widely seen as feasible, provided that targeted policies, institutional clarity, and inclusive engagement strategies are in place.

4.1.2. Stakeholder-identified concerns and challenges: qualitative insights from Q6

The qualitative responses provide additional depth to the risk perceptions identified in Q5, emphasizing stakeholder-specific concerns related to environmental, economic, and governance risks. Regarding environmental impacts, a farmer from Spain noted, “The greatest concern is using land that has already undergone desertification, which could further degrade the soil if not managed properly.” A researcher echoed this, cautioning “changing land use must be carefully managed to avoid biodiversity loss and excessive water consumption.”

Economic risks were prominent among industry and technology stakeholders. A Spanish technology provider remarked, “Investment in marginal lands is high-risk due to uncertain market demand and a lack of financial incentives.” Similarly, a policymaker from Argentina stated, “Without stable subsidies or guaranteed markets, marginal land biomass projects remain financially unsustainable.”

Governance-related challenges were frequently cited. Respondents

pointed to unclear legal frameworks, inconsistent incentive structures, and land tenure issues. A South African policymaker explained, “Land tenure issues and the lack of biomass incentive policies create major road-blocks for new investments.” An industry representative from Spain added, “Unclear legal regulations create significant uncertainties for businesses.”

Social and institutional concerns also emerged. A Spanish farmer emphasized cultural barriers, noting, “Changing the mindset of traditional agricultural communities is difficult, especially when biomass is seen as competing with food production.” A policymaker from Argentina observed, “Conflicting priorities among stakeholders make it difficult to implement an integrated approach to biomass production.”

Together, these responses reflect the complexity of deploying circular biomass models on marginal lands. Environmental degradation risks, market uncertainty, policy fragmentation, and stakeholder misalignment remain key barriers. The variation in concerns across regions and stakeholder groups underscores the need for locally adapted, inclusive strategies that address both systemic and place-based challenges.

4.2. Prioritized sustainability measures

4.2.1. Quantitative priorities by stakeholder group and country (Q7)

Fig. 5 presents stakeholder-specific sustainability priorities. Environmental & Conservation Organizations and Research, Education & Innovation Organizations gave consistently high importance to ecosystem health, biodiversity, and GHG reduction (scores of 2.0 or above). Farmers & Agricultural Sector also prioritized environmental goals but placed notable emphasis on infrastructure and job creation (1.7–2.0). Technology & Service Providers mirrored this trend, showing balanced emphasis on both innovation and environmental performance. In contrast, Industry & Bio-Based Product Companies and Investors &

Fig. 5. Sustainability priorities in circular biomass value chains on marginal lands, by stakeholder group. Stakeholder-specific priorities based on responses to Q7. Darker shades indicate higher perceived importance of each criterion. X-axis shows stakeholder categories; Y-axis shows sustainability areas.

Market Actors assigned lower scores (mostly 1.1–1.5) across all categories, with relatively more emphasis on value creation and cost reduction. Public Authorities & Policymakers showed moderate priorities across most indicators, with a slight preference toward social and institutional goals (e.g., stakeholder participation at 1.6–1.7).

Fig. 6 shows country-level differences. Stakeholders in Hungary exhibited the highest overall ratings (up to 2.5), prioritizing nearly all sustainability goals—particularly GHG reduction, ecosystem restoration, and social well-being. South Africa similarly placed high priority (≥ 2.2) on inclusive development, new jobs, and social acceptance. In Argentina, economic viability and infrastructure development were rated highest (2.3–2.4), while environmental goals received slightly lower but still positive ratings. Greece emphasized land use, local resource efficiency, and environmental goals, whereas Germany and Sweden prioritized technological improvements and institutional support. Spain consistently gave lower priority scores across most indicators, especially on institutional aspects (≤ 1.3), suggesting limited engagement with governance-focused strategies.

4.2.2. Stakeholder-suggested sustainability measures: qualitative insights from Q8

Qualitative responses reinforced the quantitative patterns, highlighting policy, financial, technological, and ecological priorities. Many stakeholders called for concrete policy actions—such as subsidies, regulatory clarity, and market incentives—to scale up sustainable practices. Environmental stakeholders emphasized ecosystem monitoring, biodiversity protection, and regenerative land use. Several respondents underlined the need for inclusive capacity-building and training programs for local actors, echoing the high ranking of social well-being and

stakeholder participation.

Direct statements further illustrate these perspectives. A policy representative from Argentina noted, “A well-defined regulatory framework is necessary to facilitate sustainable biomass markets and attract investments.” An industry actor from Spain stressed, “Carbon credit schemes and financial incentives should be expanded to ensure long-term sustainability.” A Greek farmer shared, “Institutional support is needed to help farmers transition to sustainable biomass cultivation methods,” while a researcher in Sweden remarked, “Technology-driven approaches, such as precision farming and bio-based innovations, are crucial for improving biomass value chain sustainability.”

Together, these insights emphasize the need for multi-dimensional sustainability strategies that align effective governance, financial mechanisms, and technological advancements with ecological and social priorities. Locally adapted approaches were widely advocated to ensure feasibility and long-term impact.

4.3. Quantitative patterns in stakeholder perceptions and priorities

The alignment between stakeholder concerns and sustainability priorities reveals key trade-offs that influence the feasibility of CE strategies in biomass value chains. Fig. 7 visualizes the correlations between stakeholder concerns and sustainability priorities, illustrating areas where tensions arise between environmental, economic, and social objectives.

The results indicate that environmental concerns, such as biodiversity loss, land degradation, and water availability, correlate strongly with priorities related to ecosystem restoration and land management. However, these priorities often conflict with economic considerations,

Fig. 6. Sustainability priorities in circular biomass value chains on marginal lands, by country. Country-level breakdown of sustainability priorities (Q7), highlighting differing regional focus. The intensity of color reflects the level of prioritization given by stakeholders from each country.

particularly for industry stakeholders who emphasize cost reduction and production efficiency. For instance, stakeholders concerned about soil degradation and water use stress tend to prioritize improved land use management and biodiversity conservation, whereas those focused on market stability and financial incentives prioritize economic measures such as lower production costs and new market opportunities.

Social concerns, particularly related to land ownership, rural livelihoods, and social justice, also demonstrate notable trade-offs. While stakeholders advocating for rural employment and social equity align their priorities with job creation and inclusive governance, market-driven actors prioritize investment opportunities and cost efficiency, often leading to competing objectives. Notably, public authorities and policymakers frequently link governance concerns with the need for regulatory improvements and institutional stability, as reflected in the emphasis on legal frameworks and stakeholder participation.

The visualization in Fig. 7 highlights the complexity of balancing stakeholder needs in biomass value chain development. Some sustainability priorities, such as GHG emissions reduction and resource efficiency, show broad alignment across groups, indicating areas where cooperation is more feasible. However, diverging perspectives on economic profitability, land management policies, and social equity measures suggest that targeted interventions are needed to mediate these trade-offs.

These findings emphasize the importance of designing multi-dimensional governance frameworks that integrate environmental, economic, and social considerations. By addressing key trade-offs through adaptive policy mechanisms and stakeholder dialogue, CE models in biomass value chains can become more resilient and widely

adopted.

4.4. Stakeholder needs and expectations for biobased products (Q9)

Stakeholder perspectives on biobased products reflect diverse expectations regarding economic feasibility, product quality, environmental benefits, governance structures, and social impact. These expectations play a critical role in shaping the development and scalability of CE models in biomass value chains. Table 3 categorizes key needs and expectations based on qualitative responses, highlighting stakeholder priorities and their connection to CE principles.

These findings underscore the interconnected nature of economic, environmental, and social priorities in advancing sustainable biobased production. While economic and policy stability remains central to market growth, aligning stakeholder expectations with CE models is essential for long-term adoption. The implementation of adaptive governance frameworks, targeted financial incentives, and technological innovation will be critical in balancing stakeholder needs while ensuring sustainability in marginal-land biomass value chains. By fostering cross-sector collaboration, biobased products can effectively contribute to circular production systems, climate resilience, and inclusive economic development.

4.5. Concept mapping of stakeholder priorities and governance pathways

To advance a systems-level understanding of stakeholder perspectives, a concept mapping approach was applied to synthesize qualitative insights derived from open-ended survey responses (Q4, Q6, Q8, Q9, and

Fig. 7. Alignment of stakeholder concerns with sustainability priorities in circular biomass value chains. Heatmap illustrating cross-patterns between stakeholder-rated concerns (Q5) and sustainability priorities (Q7). Darker shades reflect higher alignment, revealing areas of potential synergy or trade-off across environmental, economic, and social objectives.

Q12). These responses captured diverse stakeholder reflections on barriers, needs, priorities, and points of conflict related to circular biomass value chains on marginal lands. The concept map (Fig. 8) visualizes the interrelationships between coded stakeholder statements and six strategic domains: Governance & Policy, Economic & Market, Technical & Environmental, Circular Economy, Social & Community, and Sustainability Themes. By mapping co-occurrences among codes, the analysis illustrates how different stakeholders perceive the structural conditions for enabling circular transitions.

Governance emerged as a dominant concern across all stakeholder groups. Public Authorities & Policymakers and Industry & Bio-Based Product Companies frequently cited regulatory uncertainty, fragmented institutional arrangements, and lack of long-term incentives as key barriers to scaling circular biomass solutions. These governance-related constraints were strongly connected to economic and market concerns. Respondents emphasized the importance of coherent policy frameworks, risk-sharing instruments, and stable financing mechanisms to reduce investor hesitation. Investors & Market Actors highlighted the need for public-private partnerships, certification schemes, and

demand-side policies to strengthen market confidence in biobased products.

Technical and environmental issues were also highly interconnected in the map. Environmental & Conservation Organizations and the Farmers & Agricultural Sector stressed the importance of biodiversity protection, water conservation, and regenerative land management. These concerns were particularly prominent in regions with ecological vulnerabilities. Stakeholders across groups recognized that without strong environmental safeguards and monitoring systems, circular biomass models risk replicating unsustainable land-use practices. Technology & Service Providers and Research, Education & Innovation Organizations emphasized the need for innovation in biomass processing, improved infrastructure, and upcycling of agricultural residues to enhance system efficiency and resilience.

The social dimension surfaced through frequent co-occurrence with divergent stakeholder expectations and conflict narratives. Stakeholders from Argentina, South Africa, and Greece raised issues around land tenure, social equity, and community participation. Several emphasized that circular transitions must not only deliver environmental and

Table 3
Stakeholder needs and expectations for biobased products.

Category	Stakeholder expectations & example quotes	Circular economy connection
Economic viability & Market feasibility	Demand for stable markets, cost-competitive products, and investment incentives. <i>“Creating new market niches is crucial for industry competitiveness”</i> (Research, Spain).	Circular business models, such as closed-loop supply chains and industrial symbiosis, can stabilize markets and enhance economic resilience.
Product quality & Performance	High-quality, durable, and innovative biobased products to compete with conventional materials. <i>“Biobased products should match or exceed current industrial standards”</i> (Technology, Spain).	Advancements in material engineering and standardization enable biobased products to gain market trust and consumer acceptance.
Sustainability & Environmental priorities	Preference for low-carbon, resource-efficient products that contribute to biodiversity conservation. <i>“Environmental upgrading should be a core benefit of biobased production”</i> (Farmers, Greece).	CE principles promote regenerative agriculture, carbon sequestration, and waste valorization in biomass production.
Policy & Governance needs	Clear regulations, incentives, and certifications to support the circular bioeconomy. <i>“A well-defined regulatory framework is necessary to facilitate sustainable biomass markets”</i> (Public Authority, Argentina).	Policy alignment and certification schemes strengthen market confidence and encourage long-term investment in sustainable bioeconomy sectors.
Social & Rural Development Expectations	Support for local employment, knowledge transfer, and regional economic diversification. <i>“We need biobased industries to create rural jobs and economic opportunities”</i> (Industry, Spain).	Decentralized biobased production systems contribute to rural economic resilience, social equity, and workforce capacity-building.

economic outcomes, but also respond to local needs and avoid reinforcing existing inequalities. Calls for training programs, stakeholder inclusion in decision-making, and local capacity-building featured strongly in responses from across the spectrum of stakeholder groups.

The concept map also highlights how sustainability expectations, such as ecosystem restoration, local job creation, and transparent governance, are deeply embedded within stakeholder narratives about circular economy. These expectations reflect not only aspirational goals but also conditional factors that shape perceived feasibility. As shown in Fig. 8, nodes like “Needs & Expectations” and “Measures Prioritized” exhibit strong links to all strategic domains, underscoring the interconnected nature of stakeholder priorities.

In summary, the concept mapping analysis confirms that enabling circular biomass value chains on marginal lands requires more than isolated technological or regulatory interventions. It calls for an integrated strategy that simultaneously addresses governance gaps, economic risks, environmental safeguards, and social legitimacy. Fig. 8 offers a visual synthesis of these interdependencies, making visible the complex architecture of conditions and expectations that underpin stakeholder acceptance and long-term sustainability.

5. Discussion

This section discusses the broader implications of the results in relation to CE governance. It interprets stakeholder priorities, identifies governance gaps and sustainability trade-offs, and derives practical insights for policymaking, business strategies, and future research.

5.1. Addressing stakeholder barriers in circular biomass adoption

The results highlight several critical barriers hindering the adoption of circular biomass models, including governance constraints, market uncertainties, technological limitations, and stakeholder misalignment. Addressing these barriers requires a multi-level approach that integrates policy interventions, financial mechanisms, technological advancements, and stakeholder engagement strategies.

Stakeholder emphasis on institutional coherence, financial support, and land regeneration reflects an expanded interpretation of CE, one that goes beyond material loops and recycling to encompass system-wide governance and ecological priorities.

Regulatory and policy challenges emerge as a major concern across stakeholder groups. The lack of coherent policies and fragmented institutional frameworks create uncertainty for businesses and investors (Kirchherr et al., 2017; Geissdoerfer et al., 2017; Cong and Thomsen, 2021). Developing clear, stable, and long-term regulatory frameworks that align national policies with circular bioeconomy strategies is essential for ensuring investor confidence and facilitating market entry (D’Amato et al., 2020; Wasserbaur et al., 2022). Governments should also implement incentive structures, such as tax benefits, carbon credits, and subsidies, to reduce financial risks for businesses transitioning to circular biomass models (Millette et al., 2020; Leipold et al., 2023).

Market-related concerns, particularly around economic feasibility and demand uncertainty, underscore the need for stronger market integration mechanisms. Expanding consumer awareness and increasing the willingness to pay for biobased products can be supported through certification schemes, labeling strategies, and sustainable procurement policies (Ladu and Blind, 2017; Testa et al., 2015; Pretner et al., 2021). In addition, establishing public-private partnerships to scale up infrastructure and supply chain networks will help mitigate investment risks and enhance the competitiveness of biobased products (Nair et al., 2024; Orozco et al., 2021; Moraga et al., 2019).

Technological scalability and environmental constraints also present significant challenges. Many stakeholders emphasize the need for advancing biomass processing technologies, improving material performance, and optimizing resource efficiency (Sun et al., 2024; Stegmann et al., 2020; Kardung et al., 2021). Investments in research and innovation should focus on enhancing bio-refinery processes, precision agriculture, and waste valorization to ensure that circular biomass models are both technically and economically viable (Lokesh et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2022). Additionally, addressing environmental risks, such as soil degradation and water resource management, requires integrated land-use planning and regenerative agriculture practices to maintain ecological sustainability while expanding biomass production (Bosch et al., 2015; Haregeweyn et al., 2023). Recent research highlights the potential of valorizing residual grassland biomass as part of a cascading use strategy to enhance resource efficiency and advance circular bioeconomy objectives (Ding et al., 2024). By promoting cascading biomass use, resource valorization, and regenerative practices, circular models on marginal lands directly support SDG 12.5 objectives related to waste reduction and sustainable production.

Stakeholder coordination remains a key factor in overcoming adoption barriers. Misalignment between industry actors, policymakers, farmers, and researchers limits the efficiency of CE transitions (Oberholzer and Sachs, 2023; Winans et al., 2017). Creating collaborative governance models, including multi-stakeholder platforms, co-creation initiatives, and knowledge-sharing networks, can facilitate the alignment of different interests and accelerate the transition toward sustainable biomass value chains (Brandão and Santos, 2024; Eikeleboom, 2022). Strengthening regional governance structures and promoting cross-sector engagement will be necessary to bridge institutional gaps and foster innovation-driven adoption (Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2019; Mulya et al., 2024).

Addressing these barriers requires a systemic approach that aligns regulatory frameworks, financial incentives, technological progress, and

Fig. 8. Concept map of stakeholder priorities, governance challenges, and sustainability themes in circular biomass value chains. Integrated concept map derived from qualitative survey responses (Q4–Q9), showing key themes, interlinkages, and strategic focus areas. Grouped into five sustainability dimensions (technical, economic, environmental, social, governance).

stakeholder collaboration. By tackling these challenges holistically, circular biomass models can become more feasible, scalable, and impactful in promoting sustainable production and consumption patterns.

5.2. Policy, business and research implications

Effective policy instruments, innovative business strategies, and research support are critical to advancing both economically viable and environmentally sustainable. Policymakers should establish clear, consistent regulatory frameworks aligned with CE principles, complemented by incentive mechanisms such as subsidies, tax reliefs, and carbon credits to reduce entry risks and boost market confidence (Imbert et al., 2017; Hinderer et al., 2021; Fratini et al., 2019). Strengthening cross-sectoral collaboration through multi-stakeholder governance and regional capacity-building can also address institutional gaps and improve local implementation (D'Amato et al., 2020; Wasserbaur et al., 2022).

Business actors must move from linear to circular models by adopting closed-loop systems, resource-efficient practices, and life-cycle extensions. Strategic investments in bio-refinery infrastructure, precision agriculture and digital solutions can enhance both market competitiveness and sustainability, while also fostering transparency and stakeholder engagement (Rauter et al., 2022; Centobelli et al., 2020; Geissdoerfer et al., 2018; Perotti et al., 2025; Huynh, 2022; Parida and Vyas, 2022). Supportive business environments, including risk-sharing mechanisms and green procurement policies, can further accelerate circular adoption (Mignogna et al., 2024; Munteanu et al., 2024; Scognamiglio, 2024).

The research community plays a vital role in informing and evaluating circular transitions. Priorities include advancing adaptive governance models, mapping stakeholder alignment, and assessing the

impacts of regulations, innovations, and consumer behavior on biomass systems (Sun et al., 2024; Stegmann et al., 2020; Kardung et al., 2021). Interdisciplinary research is also essential to unpack the systemic interdependencies across policy, market, and sustainability domains (Singh et al., 2022; Lokesh et al., 2018).

By aligning these policy, business, and research efforts, stakeholders can better navigate the complexities associated with circular biomass value chains, promoting sustainable production and consumption in line with global sustainability goals, particularly those articulated in SDG 12.5.

5.3. Governance pathways for circular economy expansion

The expansion of CE models requires effective governance structures that address coordination challenges and facilitate integrated policy-making. Governance frameworks should prioritize multi-level collaboration, cross-sectoral coordination, and stakeholder engagement to drive systemic change (Geels, 2022; Ostrom, 2009; Ostrom, 2010). Recent literature emphasizes adaptive governance approaches, involving continuous learning, flexibility, and responsiveness to evolving socio-economic and environmental conditions (Termeer and Metze, 2019; Falcone et al., 2021).

Effective governance pathways also necessitate transparent communication and trust-building mechanisms among stakeholders. Establishing participatory platforms and inclusive policy dialogues can strengthen stakeholder buy-in and enable more effective implementation of CE initiatives (Ćwiklicki et al., 2024; Greer, 2022). Furthermore, leveraging technological advancements and digital tools can significantly enhance governance transparency, data-driven decision-making, and stakeholder coordination (Raggi et al., 2024). As illustrated in Fig. 8, stakeholder-identified governance and policy gaps are tightly

interlinked with economic and environmental concerns, emphasizing the need for integrated and adaptive governance pathways that address overlapping priorities and trade-offs.

Capacity-building initiatives at local and regional levels are essential to empower actors in CE transitions. Training programs, knowledge exchange networks, and institutional capacity development can help address skill gaps, enhance policy coherence, and accelerate CE adoption (Schot and Steinmueller, 2018; de Jesus & Mendonça, 2021). Finally, international collaboration and policy learning across regions and sectors can support broader dissemination of successful governance strategies and best practices, contributing to global CE expansion (Lieder and Rashid, 2016; Pinyol Alberich and Hartley, 2024).

5.4. Comparison to existing research and contribution

This study extends existing research on circular biomass value chains by integrating stakeholder perspectives across diverse geographical and sectoral contexts, highlighting unique insights into governance challenges, market dynamics, and technological barriers. Compared to prior studies, which typically focus on single dimensions such as policy frameworks or technological innovation (Kalmykova et al., 2018; Merli et al., 2018), this research adopts a holistic perspective—simultaneously addressing governance structures, business model innovation, and technical-environmental considerations (Raggi et al., 2024; Marsh et al., 2022).

While previous research has often emphasized individual components, recent literature increasingly advocates for integrated analyses that combine economic, policy, and technological factors to foster CE transitions (Du et al., 2024; Ul-Durar et al., 2023; Mehmood et al., 2021; Urbinati et al., 2017). This study contributes to that discourse by providing empirical insights that bridge theoretical frameworks with stakeholder experiences, enriching our understanding of the systemic interactions underpinning circular biomass adoption (Calisto Friant et al., 2024; Henry and Bauwens, 2022; Borrello et al., 2020).

This research also responds to identified gaps in stakeholder-oriented CE literature, particularly regarding how multi-level governance systems interact with localized priorities. Prior studies have often focused on technical feasibility (Kirchherr et al., 2017), business models (Centobelli et al., 2020), and material efficiency strategies (Haupt et al., 2017), whereas this study highlights the critical importance of cross-sectoral collaboration and institutional coherence in circular transitions (Oberholzer and Sachs, 2023; Benz, 2022; Bauwens et al., 2020). Rather than examining these elements in isolation, the analysis emphasizes their interconnected nature and the need to align global sustainability goals with local governance capacities and stakeholder expectations.

By systematically examining stakeholder concerns, sustainability priorities, and governance constraints, this research contributes to a growing body of literature that calls for inclusive, participatory, and context-sensitive approaches to CE transitions (Marino and Pariso, 2020; Bocken, 2024; Moreau et al., 2017). It also strengthens prior findings by expanding the scope of analysis to include institutional barriers and policy inconsistencies that influence stakeholder engagement and value chain development (Dreyer et al., 2017; Donner and de Vries, 2021).

The concept mapping approach adopted in this study further differentiates it from earlier works by identifying both conflicts and synergies among stakeholder groups. This aligns with recent trends emphasizing stakeholder-driven governance and business model innovation as key mechanisms for overcoming implementation barriers in the CE (Hofmann, 2019; Ranta et al., 2018).

Ultimately, this study advances CE scholarship by integrating empirical stakeholder perspectives into a multi-dimensional analysis of governance, business models, and sustainability priorities, particularly in the underexplored context of biomass value chains on marginal lands.

5.5. Limitations and future research

Despite the valuable insights generated through this study, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the qualitative and stakeholder-driven nature of the research provides in-depth, context-rich perspectives but limits the generalizability of findings across broader geographic, policy, or sectoral settings. The results reflect specific local conditions and stakeholder dynamics within seven case studies and should therefore be interpreted with caution when extrapolating to other regions or biomass systems.

Second, the relatively small and uneven distribution of survey respondents across countries and stakeholder groups may have constrained the representativeness of the findings. In particular, underrepresentation of actors such as investors, funding institutions, and local public authorities may have limited the visibility of certain governance or financial perspectives. While the analysis accounted for this imbalance through triangulation and quantitative inclusion, response bias cannot be entirely ruled out and may have influenced the prominence of certain perspectives. The triangulated mixed-method design helped to surface minority viewpoints despite their lower representation. In addition, as the survey focused broadly on stakeholder views regarding the use of marginal lands for sustainable biomass value chains, some responses may reflect varying levels of familiarity with CE concepts. These concepts were not explicitly defined in the questionnaire but were applied through the analytical framework to interpret priorities and barriers.

Third, although the survey was translated into local languages by native-speaking project partners and back-translated into English to ensure analytical consistency (see Section 3.2), subtle linguistic and cultural variations may have influenced the interpretation of key terms such as “sustainability,” “regenerative use,” or “value chain development.”

Finally, the study did not include quantitative modeling approaches such as life cycle assessment (LCA), cost-benefit analysis (CBA), or environmental simulations. While the mixed-method design offered robust triangulation of stakeholder perspectives, future studies would benefit from complementing such qualitative approaches with empirical modeling to validate sustainability claims and assess systemic trade-offs.

Future research should aim to address these limitations by expanding the geographical scope, improving stakeholder group representation, and employing longitudinal or comparative case study designs to track evolving stakeholder perspectives and governance arrangements. In particular, further attention to Global South contexts could enrich understanding of social equity, institutional readiness, and capacity-building needs in CE implementation. Moreover, exploring how digital tools, behavioral interventions, and cross-sectoral policy learning can support alignment across stakeholder groups would provide additional practical insights to accelerate the transition to circular biomass systems.

6. Conclusion

This study explored stakeholder-defined challenges, priorities, and governance needs for implementing CE models in biomass-based value chains on marginal lands. Based on comparative analysis across seven case studies in Europe, South Africa, and Argentina, the findings reveal systemic tensions between economic feasibility, ecological restoration, and social equity. These tensions vary across contexts and stakeholder groups, reflecting the complex trade-offs involved in operationalizing CE models in marginal environments.

Businesses and investors emphasized the importance of market stability, infrastructure, and financial incentives to de-risk investment and support uptake. Farmers and land managers highlighted long-term support mechanisms, flexible land-use policies, and fair compensation. Policymakers and environmental and conservation organizations prioritized regulatory coherence, biodiversity protection, and

participatory governance, while research and innovation actors underscored the need for coordination, inclusive knowledge-sharing platforms, and localized monitoring tools. In Global South contexts, concerns around land tenure, access to finance, and equity in participation and benefit-sharing were especially prominent. Stakeholders also articulated expectations for biobased products that align with local sustainability needs, offer biodiversity and climate benefits, and meet standards for affordability, traceability, and circular value.

Concept mapping confirmed that stakeholder governance is critical for integrating technical, institutional, and economic dimensions of circular transitions. Advancing circular bioeconomy models on marginal lands requires cross-sectoral collaboration, adaptive policy design, inclusive value chain development, and stable financial instruments tailored to diverse regional conditions.

To support implementation, the study recommends that policymakers establish coherent regulatory frameworks and long-term funding mechanisms; that businesses and investors engage in co-designing context-aware CE models; and that research and environmental actors are supported in developing inclusive monitoring systems and sustainability assessment tools. Future research should investigate how governance innovations and stakeholder alignment evolve over time and evaluate their impacts on circularity, resilience, and social outcomes. In particular, how do policy instruments influence stakeholder alignment in diverse marginal land contexts? What forms of participatory governance best support both equity and circularity in biomass value chains? These findings advance stakeholder-driven models for sustainable production and reinforce alignment with SDG 12.5 and complementary environmental goals under SDGs 13 and 15.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Thi Huyen Trang Dam: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Philipp Grundmann:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Richard Orozco:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Naser Reyhani:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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